

AN ENGINEERING APPROACH TO UPGRADE NOAA'S TIDAL OBSERVATION NETWORK INSTRUMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the evolution and ongoing engineering effort to increase instrument reliability and maintain high data quality in NOAA's National Tide and Water Level Observation Network. In 1978, data sets were below desired quality because extensive processing was necessary to obtain the required data products. A corrective maintenance program was initiated to provide an immediate short term solution. Parallel efforts to correct manufacturing design deficiencies and improve long term reliability were initiated. Modified instruments were then subjected to a rigorous reliability test program. The successful test results provided the impetus to undertake a pilot project to upgrade a portion of the Network in conjunction with the introduction of an Integrated Logistics Support Plan. In 1979, over 60 stations were upgraded with a significant increase in the reliability and data quality. An additional two hundred stations were designated for upgrade in 1980. In 1981, the pilot project is transitioning into an upgrade program to complete the entire network.

INTRODUCTION

The Engineering Development Office (EDO), Ocean Technology and Engineering Services (OTES), of NOAA has a major role in upgrading the engineering aspects of the National Tides and Water Levels Observation Network's field instrumentation and logistics support. The Network is operated and maintained by the National Ocean Survey (NOS) of NOAA for the purpose of providing a variety of timely and cost effective tidal information products of high quality. The Network was established in the early 1800's and has since expanded to include 140 Primary Tide Stations and 35 Great Lakes Water Level Stations which are permanently installed. In addition, a fluctuating number of subordinate stations are operated each year for various durations depending on mission requirements. With the advent of cooperative State Marine Boundary Determination Programs within the past 10 years, the number of subordinate stations rapidly expanded to approximately 250 per year and presently numbers about 150. The operational constraints imposed on tidal measurement instrumentation are varied and usually quite severe since the Network covers the complete range of coastal and near-shore marine environments of the U. S. and its territories.

This transforms into performance requirements which are typically incompatible with a single low cost commercial instrument. Additionally, since the inception of automatic instrumentation in the mid 1800's, continuous data sets have been sought for specific durations. Thus, at the Primary Station a 19 year time series is generally required for the future prediction of tides in that geographical area. This will include the seasonal variations as well as the various astronomic configurations of the sun, moon and earth. Time series from 3 months to 1 year are required at a subordinate station for the determination of a tidal datum for a marine boundary using the method of simultaneous comparison to a Primary Station in the vicinity. Shorter term subordinate stations collect tidal data which are used to correct measured soundings for Hydrographic charting. Data breaks in any of these time series present serious problems both in processing time and analysis accuracy. The worst effect of a data break would be a Hydrographic resurvey since the required tidal correctors could not be applied to the survey vessels depth soundings. An added requirement is that this same time series recording instrumentation must also be capable of telemetry in real time or transmission in near real time for a variety of special applications. Real time tidal data are mandatory for early Tsunami warning throughout the Pacific Islands and have been provided since the late 1940's. Similarly, emergency flood warnings are issued by NOAA based on storm tides and river flood stages telemetered or transmitted and quickly programmed into special analytical flood models developed for the Eastern and Gulf coastal areas. Emerging requirements are being identified for real time tidal information to assist harbor traffic controllers and vessel masters for safe piloting in highly congested or restricted navigation areas.

The demand for timely and cost effective tidal information products of high quality has dramatically increased over the past decade and is directly linked to the reliability and maintainability of the tidal measurement system instrumentation. These are in turn a function of the logistics support system including an appropriate level of resources. The engineering and logistics inherent in the long term operation of a large number of commercially available instruments have rarely been adequately addressed by any organization in the oceanographic community. This is not a startling realization

given that few oceanographic parameters are measured both spatially and temporally on the magnitude of a National Tide and Water Levels Network. If they are, the operational managers are reluctant to develop and use a yardstick with which to measure their system's data quality and cost effectiveness. Hence, the engineering and management methods employed by other organizations engaged in large scale systems are logical models to apply to oceanographic instrumentation systems in general. The extensive logistics support plans developed by the various branches of the U. S. Military are prime examples. Instrument reliability and maintainability became paramount areas of concern to NOS when severe environmental conditions visibly degraded field instrument performance and data quality. In 1978, NOS realized that data sets received from these instruments were below desired quality because extensive processing was necessary to obtain the required NOAA data products. Also, tide recorders were frequently failing within three months of installation. An assessment of the failure modes and a corrective maintenance program was initiated by EDO to provide an immediate short term solution and avoid loss of valuable data sets. In parallel, a development program to correct manufacturing design deficiencies and improve long term reliability was initiated. Modified tide recorders were then subjected to a rigorous field reliability test program which is still ongoing 29 months after installation and has demonstrated significant improvement in overall performance in a worst case environment. The successful results obtained in the development and test programs provided the impetus for NOS to undertake a pilot project to upgrade a portion of the National Tide and Water Level Observation Network. The pilot project implemented the engineering modifications with preventative maintenance and refurbishment of the tide recorders, in conjunction with data quality control checks, operation procedures, personnel training, and introduction of an Integrated Logistics Support Plan. In 1979, over 60 stations were designated and upgraded in the pilot project, with a significant increase in the reliability and quality of field data acquired. An additional two hundred stations were designated for upgrade in 1980. In 1981, the pilot project is transitioning into an upgrade program to complete the entire network. The following sections briefly describe the instrumentation system, engineering activities and results over the past four years which have allowed NOS to continue providing timely and cost effective tidal information products of high quality.

INSTRUMENTATION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Each NOS Primary Tide Station utilizes commercially available tide recording instrumentation housed in a small permanent structure constructed over a stilling well. The stilling well with orifice serves as a mechanical filter to dampen out higher frequency water level fluctuations. Tidal motion is transferred from a float inside the stilling well via a cable system to the recording and sometimes transmitting instrument. The instruments are electromechanical

devices commonly referred to as Analog-to-Digital Recorders (ADR). Each transforms the analog tidal signal through a mechanical encoder to a 16 digit BCD value. Discrete values are punched on foilbacked paper tape at 6 minute intervals and coordinated to local standard time. The subordinate stations utilize the same instrumentation housed in portable weatherproof shelters and mounted on smaller stilling wells. Tidal data from both types of stations are directly related to the National Geodetic Vertical Datum Network through a series of human observations of a tide staff which is precisely surveyed-in. Figure 1 describes both the Primary and subordinate station configurations in use by NOS. Periodic and daily human interface with the instrumentation is required. The periodic interfaces include installation, removal, and preventative or corrective maintenance. The daily interface includes verification of instrument performance and a calibration function with respect to the tide staff known as the daily observation. After a monthly time series is collected, the method of comparative readings between the ADR raw data and the daily observations is applied in the analysis process. Ultimately computer generated tidal statistics are adjusted and referenced to the staff and benchmarks at each station. Every part of the field system has unique reliability and maintainability requirements, constraints and problem areas which must be realistically engineered for and carefully managed to guarantee the level of output products required by NOS and the user community.

DATA COLLECTION PROBLEMS

Data collection problems were identified in four general areas by NOS in 1978. As each data set was received from the field, a preliminary evaluation of the punched paper tape record was conducted by the NOS analysis group which categorized these problems. Although somewhat subjective, the four areas included; 1) mechanical and paper tape problems, 2) power and time problems, 3) observer and staff relationship problems, and 4) operational problems related to stilling wells and support hardware. Data defects caused by these problem areas resulted in increased analysis resources, a decrease in the timeliness of the output products and, in some cases, necessitated recollection or extended subordinate station operation with a repaired or replacement instrument. A brief overview of these four problem areas with the short term solutions initiated by EDO follows. Long term solutions will be discussed later under the Integrated Logistics Support Plan and Upgrade Project sections.

The mechanical problem areas included design deficiencies, improper material selection for the marine environment and a variety of critical adjustment functions for which either proper training, parts or tools were not provided. Instrument deterioration over one to two years of field operation on a subordinate station becomes evident in the data as the "stepping problem,"

i.e., a plot of the digital data resembling a staircase as opposed to a sinusoid. The near ocean salt air environment contributed to bearing and general hardware deterioration due to incompatible materials and lubrication deficiencies. Instruments were designed and assembled with unlubricated open race bearings due to extremely low torque requirements. In combination with dissimilar materials within and adjacent to the bearings, four failure modes were identified and verified by various bearing manufacturers. These included fretting, galvanic and general wasting corrosion and brinelling. Bearing deterioration subsequently affected the extremely low torque values inherent in the gage design and "steps" resulted in the data. The short term solution included simple torque tests to identify the problem, repair, training, parts and special tool provisioning. Following the repair, acceptance testing was required before redeployment.

The paper tape problems were related to defective paper from the supplier and a variety of environmental factors which caused the close tolerance punching and paper transport mechanism to progressively fail. Paper inspection procedures and punch mechanism tests were initiated to quantify this problem. Controlling the localized instrument environment to avoid humidity problems was investigated but proved difficult since the daily observation function was required.

Resolving timer problems was the subject of an ongoing separate EDO developmental effort to replace factory supplied timers with more accurate and reliable units. The testing of prototype units was being successfully completed when the instrumentation problems became important so a ready solution was available for implementation. Power problems were quickly identified as overuse of battery packs and subsequent failure. Also low temperature operational limits were not accounted for in the field. Design efforts were initiated for an inexpensive audio battery voltage monitor for daily observer use, while existing batteries in the field were replaced more frequently.

Observer problems included incorrect or missing observations, incorrect procedures and staff relationship discrepancies. These problems were the most readily identified during the preliminary evaluation and were usually directly linked to the skill level, training and pay schedule of the observer hired by NOS at each station.

The operational problems resulted from rapid expansion of the subordinate station portion of the National Network without a commensurate increase in the level of resources. Consequently, corrective maintenance became standard operational practice as opposed to more frequent field verification and preventative maintenance. This was compounded by non-standard subordinate station stilling well design and operation under extreme winter conditions. Mechanical instrument problems resulted from frozen stilling wells which were incorrectly attributed to the instrument and

not the environment. The underlying source of all of the above data collection problems was the lack of a total system engineering approach in conjunction with a well defined and managed Integrated Logistics Support Plan. While the short term solutions eliminated visible data defects, it was evident that a major operational philosophy change was required.

INTEGRATED LOGISTICS SUPPORT PLAN

The need for an Integrated Logistics Support Plan (ILSP) for the National Tide and Water Level Observation Network was identified in late 1978. A commitment was secured from NOS that if such a plan was developed, the resources would be made available to implement it. The ILSP effort was initiated in early 1979 in conjunction with resolving the long term instrumentation reliability and maintainability problems. Integrated Logistics Support is defined as a process which identifies in a systematic and orderly manner those functions and resources necessary for the support of the operation and maintenance of existing tides and water level measurement systems. The previous support was non-systematic because of different standards and philosophies and different levels of training and experience. The objectives of the ILSP development were to provide standardized documentation throughout NOS and use a systematic approach of instrument support. A transition from corrective to preventative maintenance was required and skill levels and training requirements had to be established. Most importantly, a management feedback mechanism analyzing maintenance resources versus data quality had to be initiated, i.e., the yardstick.

The first edition ILSP was developed by EDO in conjunction with the experience and recommendations of the instrument manufacturers, the NOS Marine Centers, headquarters elements, field parties and many others involved in the National Network. The ILSP addresses maintenance reporting, observation functions, training, parts provisioning, instrument maintenance and technical specifications. As other elements of the National Network are adequately addressed each will be included in the ILSP. Highlights of the ILSP relative to the engineering upgrade include a set of Data Standards and a catalog of Data Defects. These items remove the subjectivity during Preliminary Evaluation of incoming data and provide a computer summary of all data defects for monthly evaluation of the total Network. Probable causes can then be promptly relayed to the field maintenance personnel for quick reaction repairs. Shop and field personnel in turn are utilizing a similar system called FAILog. All maintenance functions are documented on a standardized form and entered into another data base for computerized maintenance analysis. Personnel qualifications standards and training programs for all field activities also were provided in the training section of the ILSP. Finally, a complete volume is devoted to maintenance support which presently includes 30 detailed technical procedures. These cover

instrumentation trouble shooting, major refurbishment, specialized component maintenance, acceptance testing and field performance verification.

RELIABILITY AND MAINTAINABILITY TESTING

A two phase test program was designed to evaluate instrumentation modifications considered essential to increase long term reliability. The first phase of the test program was an accelerated field performance test of eight modified instruments with newly designed support hardware based on statistical sampling criteria. Once performance was established under worst case conditions, the test continued into a second phase to establish field deterioration and maintenance intervals. Conclusive proof was sought that modified test gages would give quality tide data under worst case field conditions with resource requirements that could be established as a function of time. This proof, together with the known modification costs, would be used to decide whether modified instruments would be an improvement over the larger number of operational unmodified gages which were being periodically tested and maintained. The test was designed to compare a new ADR operational philosophy which required a larger initial expenditure to obtain a longer maintenance interval and lower lifetime cost, against the existing operating philosophy which has high long term costs and risks associated with frequent repetitive maintenance.

Test site criteria were first chosen based on worst case environmental conditions and reasonable logistic constraints. These criteria were then prioritized and a simple weight factor system established. Potential sites were then established and site surveys were conducted on the majority of sites proposed. Indian River Inlet, Delaware, with the highest weight factor was chosen as the test site. Eight ADRs were identically modified beginning in late 1978. The eight recorders were randomly chosen from the NOS inventory. In general, each was manufactured and purchased in 1976 and had approximately 1 to 1.5 years of field use on subordinate stations in either New Jersey, Florida or Texas. Four of the recorders had recent corrective maintenance.

There were four modifications that are worthy of mention. The first was the precision counter boring of the encoder drums to accept precision low torque sealed and lubricated bearings to solve the "stepping" problem. The second was gear related to provide smoother transition of encoder motion. The third was a coupling modification and spring replacement in combination with float and stilling well modifications. These accommodated increased float response and alleviated recorder damage in freezing conditions in conjunction with kerosene addition to the stilling well. The fourth included a salt air environment material protection system for the ADR inner and outer covers. All eight recorders were refurbished during the course of the modification according to preliminary procedures of the ILSP. Following modification and refurbishment, each ADR was

acceptance tested as a mandatory quality control measure.

In November 1978, frameworks and eight stilling wells were installed adjacent to the existing NOS Primary Tide Station at the U.S. Coast Guard Base, Indian River Inlet, Delaware. The eight modified and acceptance tested ADRs were installed in December 1978. Figure 2 shows details of the test installation. The existing tide observer was trained to perform the routine NOS required digital recorder and staff observations twenty times a month on all test recorders. A ninth instrument was installed in March 1979 to evaluate a special stilling well orifice modification and was added to the test statistics. Between December 1978 and June 1981, all modified ADRs were inspected on a 1 to 2 month basis and tested in accordance with the ILSP. The field tests were designed to identify deterioration trends and establish reliability and maintainability statistics.

Torque Test 1 (Pull Release Test) was designed as a system test which measures digital recorder torque which float movement and subsequent force must overcome. Figure 3 is an example of the time series of Torque Test 1 values over 29 months of operation. Included are the initial condition and 15 subsequent field test values. The time series shows the pull value, release value and the difference (Δ) for each test. The failure criteria for Torque Test 1 was specified before the field installation as Δ not to exceed 2 oz. The maximum Δ value for Test 2 was 1.25 oz, and occurred at 3, 10.5 and 24 months. The example in Figure 3 is representative of all 9 test recorders over the test period.

Torque Test 2 was designed in two parts. Running torque tracks specific bearing deterioration. Hard Spot torque tracks the influence of critical tolerances and gears. Figure 4 is an example of the time series of Torque Test 2 values over 29 months of operation. Included are the initial condition and 16 subsequent field test values. The time series shows the test values in both clockwise and counterclockwise directions and represents the running torque required to resolve 0.01 and 0.1 ft. of encoder mechanism motion. During the first two months of testing, the procedure was modified by fabricating a test fixture to remove the undesirable variable of float-reel imbalance between test recorders. The magnitude of the imbalance is shown in the first two data points. Values of 6 to 8 oz. were reduced to 2 oz. which continue over the course of the test. The ILSP acceptance testing criteria for Torque Test 2 was subsequently specified at 2 to 4 oz. using this method. The failure criteria for Torque Test 2 (both running and hard spot) was specified before field installation as not to exceed 16 oz. The running torque has not significantly changed over the course of the test as seen in the example. The example is representative of all 9 test recorders over the test period.

ADR UPGRADE PILOT PROJECT

Based on the success of the accelerated portion of the reliability testing in early 1979, a Pilot Project was instituted in mid 1979. The project objective was to implement the ADR engineering upgrades in four controlled areas of the National Network in conjunction with the ILSP. The areas included all Primary Tide Stations in Florida, the Gulf Coast and California and one-half of the subordinate stations in the South Carolina Marine Boundary Program. A goal of reducing the defective data fraction to the 20 percent level was set. The Pilot Project targeted 60 ADRs for modification and refurbishment, acceptance testing, and field commissioning. Management, training and parts provisioning was conducted with NOS Headquarters, Marine Centers and Field Party involvement under the ILSP. A result evaluation task was established to assess the improvements which contributed most significantly to the reduced defective data fraction for future total network upgrade purposes. The results evaluation task was charged with reporting Pilot Project status to a high level NOS Review Board. A Review Board meeting covering the status of the Pilot Project was held in November 1980. A summary of 354 station months of upgrade ADR data was compared to 434 station months of data for unmodified ADRs. The modified and unmodified gages were both operating under the ILSP. A comparison between the upgraded and unmodified showed a fractional success (records with no defects or insignificant defects) of 26% versus 14%. When expanded to look at Data Defect Factors (DDFs) below 1 (1 additional hour of processing) the fractional successes increase to 70% versus 58% respectively. When expanded to look at DDFs below 2 (2 additional hours of processing) the fractional successes increase to 86% versus 80% respectively. Other project success indicators were presented. These included the overall decrease in the percentage of station months which would not reduce to mean values for datum determination from 40% in 1978 to 10% in 1980, with Oct. 1980 at the 4% level. This indicator shows an overall decline in defective field data based on all system improvements including the Pilot Project. The Review Board recommended to continue the Pilot Project activities based on the preliminary data improvement trends indicated.

PRESENT STATUS

The Results Evaluation task completed a revised Data Defect Factor time test and updated all factors in March 1981. A defect free monthly tidal data set presently requires an average value of 2 hours to process based on all types of tides and personnel skill levels in the NOS analysis branch. Defects require 3/4 of an hour additional analysis and processing time. 262 ADRs have been modified during the course of the Pilot Project which is transitioning into an Upgrade Program to complete the total National Tide and Water Level Network within the next two years.

Figure 1. Typical NOS Tide Station

Figure 2. Test Installation at the U. S. Coast Guard Station, Indian River Inlet, Delaware

Figure 3. Torque Test #1 Time Series

Figure 4. Torque Test #2 Time Series